

Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow

(A Central University)

One Day National Seminar

on

ADVANCING RIGHT TO FOOD SECURITY AND NUTRITION IN INDIA: HUMAN RIGHTS PERSPECTIVE

on

January 21, 2026

Organised by

DEPARTMENT OF LAW

in collaboration with

NATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS COMMISSION (NHRC), INDIA

(TECHNICAL SESSION – 1)

ONLINE PARTICIPANTS LIST FOR SEMINAR

Sr. No.	Name Of The Participant	Institution/ Affiliation	Topic	Signature
1	Dr Maroof Bashir (Principal)	St.Wilfreds College Of Law, Panvel, New Mumbai	Advancing Right To Food Security And Nutrition In India: Human Right Perspective	
2	Mrs. Ashwini Amol Patil (Assistant Professor)	St.Wilfreds College Of Law, Panvel, New Mumbai	Advancing Right To Food Security And Nutrition In India: Human Right Perspective	
3	Abhishakti Srivastava (Pg Student)	University Of Allahabad	Nutritional Adequacy Of The Mid-Day Meal Scheme: A Rights-Based Approach	
4	Abhai Raj Shukla (Pg Student)	University Of Allahabad	Nutritional Adequacy Of The Mid-Day Meal Scheme: A Rights-Based Approach	
5	Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar (Students)	Central University Of Haryana Haryana	Right To Food As A Human Right In India: Legal Framework, Social Accountability, And The Road Towards Viksit Bharat @2047	
6	Shreyashi Srivastava (Pg (Llm 1 Year) Student)	Babasaheb Bhim Rao Ambedkar University.	Food Security In The Framework Of Social Determinants Of Health.	
7	Maitra Varun Chotia (Research Scholar)	Central Sanskrit University	Food, Dignity And The Constitution: Enforcing Nutritional Standards Under India's Food Security Framework	
8	Simran Gupta(3rd Year Bba.Ll.B(H) Student)	Amity University Jharkhand	Public Distribution System (Pds) Under The National Food Security Act, 2013: Legal Framework And Implementation Challenges For	

			Tribal And Remote Populations In India	
9	Dr. Amrita Singh(Assistant Professor)	Indira Gandhi National Tribal University	Role Of Self-Help Groups (Shgs) In Food Security: With Special Reference To Tribal Women Of Anuppur District	
10	Pon Thulasi C (Student)	Joy University	Public Interest Litigation And Enforcement Of The Right To Food In India : A Human Right Perspective	
11	Dr. Dinusha Masil F (Assistant Professor)	Joy University	Public Interest Litigation And Enforcement Of The Right To Food In India : A Human Right Perspective	
12	Neethu M (Research Scholar)	Vels Institute Of Science, Technology And Advanced Studies (Vistas)	Effectiveness Of The Public Distribution System In Ensuring Food Security Under Nfsa,2013	
13	Srishti Saxena (Student)	Atal Bihari Vajpayee School Of Legal Studies Csjm Kanpur	Understanding Law In The Contemporary Context	
14	Swarnima Singh Tomar (Phd Scholar)	Amity Law School Amity University Lucknow Campus	Ensuring The Right To Food Security And Nutrition For Transgender Persons In India: A Socio-Legal Analysis Under The Transgender Persons (Protection Of Rights) Act, 2019 And Food Security Laws	
15	Dr Jyoti Yadav (Assistant Professor)	Amity Law School Amity University Lucknow Campus	Ensuring The Right To Food Security And Nutrition For Transgender Persons In India: A Socio-Legal Analysis Under The Transgender Persons (Protection Of Rights) Act, 2019 And Food Security Laws	
16	Ms. Diksha Taneja (Research Scholar)	Faculty Of Juridical Sciences, Rama University	Food Security, Digital Surveillance, And National Security: A Constitutional Analysis Of Welfare Governance In India	
17	Sakshi Singh	Babasaheb Bhimrao	Constitutional And Legal Foundation On Right To Food In	

	(Student)	Ambedkar University	India.	
18	Dr. Azhar Ali Khan (Asst. Professor)	Department Of Law, Agra College, Agra	Food Adulteration In India Challenging The Basic Constitutional Imperatives: An Overview	
19	Apurv Bhardwaj (Ph.D. Scholar)	Law Faculty, Agra College, Agra	Right To Food Security Under The Indian Constitution: An Appraisal	
20	Prachi Singh (Research Scholar)	Ifhe Law School, Hyderabad	Implementation And Impact Of The National Food Security Act 2013	
21	Deepika Nallabelli (Research Scholar)	Kakatiya University, Warangal	Implementation And Impact Of The National Food Security Act 2013	
22	Rahul Singh (Research Scholar)	Fjs, Rama University	Judicial Activism And Evolution Of Right To Food: A Critical Analysis Of Indian Supreme Court Jurisprudence	
23	Ms. Diksha Taneja(Research Scholar)	Fjs,Rama University	Judicial Activism And Evolution Of Right To Food: A Critical Analysis Of Indian Supreme Court Jurisprudence	
24	Dr. Sushil Kumar (Assistant Professor)	Faculty Of Law, University Of Lucknow	From Welfare To Entitlement: Rights-Based Governance In Food Security Programs	
25	Dr. Sandhya Rani (Assistant Professor)	Amity University Gurgaon	From Welfare To Entitlement: Rights-Based Governance In Food Security Programs	
26	Rupa Upadhyay (Professor)	Lady Irwin College, University Of Delhi	Organic Food Consumption And Food Security: A Consumer Perspective	
27	Ambika Chaudhary (Research Scholar)	Lady Irwin College, University Of Delhi	Organic Food Consumption And Food Security: A Consumer Perspective	
28	Chandan Singh (Assistant Professor)	Government College Uklana, (Hisar)	Strengthening Food Security: Analysing The Role Of Right To Public Services Guarantee Acts In Operationalizing The National Food Security Act, 2013	

29	Huma Ausaf (Research Scholar)	Integral University	Food Security And Nutrition As Public Health Imperatives: Realizing The Human Right To Food In India	
30	Dr. Manzoor Khan (Assistant Professor)	Integral University	Food Security And Nutrition As Public Health Imperatives: Realizing The Human Right To Food In India	
31	Dr. Upendra Grewal (Assistant Professor)	Iftm University, Moradabad	Constitutional Dimensions Of Right To Food In India	
32	Badar Ahmad (Professor, Department Of Law)	Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh	Ensuring Human Dignity Through Right To Food In India: A Judicial Perspective	
33	Mukesh Kumar Gaur (Research Scholar)	Dept. Of Law, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh	Ensuring Human Dignity Through Right To Food In India: A Judicial Perspective	
34	Prof. Adesh Kumar (Dean, Faculty Of Law, University Of Allahabad, Prayagraj)	University Of Allahabad, Prayagraj	Right To Food Vis-A-Vis Children Of Incarcerated Mothers: An Indian Perspective.	
35	Ms. Deepti Sen (Senior Research Fellow, Faculty Of Law, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi)	Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi	Right To Food Vis-A-Vis Children Of Incarcerated Mothers: An Indian Perspective.	
36	Aishwarya Kamyia Singh (Advocate/Professional)	Delhi Bar Council	Seeds Of Equality: Women's Land Rights As The Missing Link In India's Right To Food	
37	Gaurav Suman (Ph.D.(Law))	Law School, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi	'Future Of Zero-Waste Food Supply Chains'	
38	Arzu Nayab (Student Of L.I.M.)	Faculty Of Law, University Of Lucknow	From Welfare To Rights: Evolution Of Food Security Laws In The Indian Sub-Continent	
39	Swaraj Shukla (Student Of L.I.M.)	Faculty Of Law, University Of Lucknow	From Welfare To Rights: Evolution Of Food Security Laws In The Indian Sub-Continent	
40	Nikita Sharma (Research Scholar)	Maharashtra National Law University, Nagpur	Combating Malnutrition: The Role Of Food Fortification And Policy Interventions In India	
41	Satyabhama (Research	Nehru Gram Bharti (Deemed	Advancing Right To Food Security And Nutrition In India: Human	

	Scholar)	To Be University) Prayagraj	Rights Perspective	
42	Anuj (Student)	Bbau Lucknow	Advancing Right To Food Security And Nutrition In India : Human Rights Perspective	
43	Sana Afreen (Assistant Professor)	Era University	Attending The Seminar.	
44	Anshul Gautam (Alumini)	Jiwaji University, Gwalior <M.P>	Nil	
45	Shiva Malakar (Student)	Faculty Of Law, University Of Lucknow, Lucknow	Food Rights : Health And Legal Provisions	
46	Rohan Kumar (Student)	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow	A Human Rights Perspective On Social Accountability And Transparency In Food Security Programs.	
47	Harsh Singh (Student)	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University	Legal And Nutritional Implications Of The Mid-Day Meal Scheme.	
48	Varnika Singh (Student)	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar Central University	Climate Change And Environmental Impacts On Food Security	
49	Ranjana Kumari (Student)	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar Central University	Advancing Right To Food Security And Nutrition In India Human Right Perspective	
50	Shivangi Singh (Student)	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar Central University	Advancing Right To Food Security And Nutrition In India : Human Rights Perspection	
51	Varsha Singh(Research Scholar)	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar Central University	Human Rights	
52				
53				

54				
55				
56				
57				
58				
59				
60				
61				
62				
63				
64				
65				
66				
67				
68				
69				
70				
71				
72				
73				
74				
75				
76				
77				
78				
79				
80				
81				
82				
83				

84				
85				
86				
87				
88				
89				
90				
91				
92				
93				
94				
95				
96				
97				
98				
99				
100				
101				
102				
103				
104				
105				
106				
107				
108				
109				
110				
111				
112				
113				

114				
115				
116				
117				
118				
119				
120				
121				
122				
123				
124				
125				
126				
127				
128				
129				
130				
131				
132				
133				
134				
135				
136				
137				
138				
139				
140				
141				
142				
143				

144				
145				
146				
147				
148				
149				